

Technical efficiency and production risk in Scottish Agriculture: Impacts on the livestock & arable sectors

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Executive Summary

Technical efficiency and production risk are both important measures of farm performance. Technical efficiency identifies which farms do more with less, while production risk identifies uncertainty and variability in farm outputs and can be considered a key aspect of farm resilience.

Using the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data from 2003–2022 we calculate farm technical efficiency while accounting for production risk. This enables us to identify the prevalence of production inefficiency and production risk, which is related to farms' resilience capacity. We also explore factors associated with higher technical efficiency and lower production risk. While some interventions might contribute to improving technical efficiency and reducing production risk e.g. crop diversification, others might better address technical efficiency e.g. land reform to support long-term investment, or production risk e.g. crop insurance. By considering these performance indicators together we can better diagnose the challenges facing farms in Scotland.

The main finding is that farm performance in Scottish agriculture has been highly volatile and there are few common drivers of farm performance across different farm types. Production risk is highly prevalent in livestock farming systems while technical inefficiency is pronounced in arable farms. This means that policy intervention should focus more on ensuring business stability and resilience in the livestock farming sector and reducing production in-efficiency in the arable farming sector.

One key factor that stands out in determining farm performance is the share of subsidy to total farm income. Farms where the share of subsidy to total farm income is high tend to be more technically inefficient; however, they also tend to have lower levels of production risk. Policymakers should ensure that new subsidy regimes implemented under the Agricultural Reform Bill continue to support farms by helping to mitigate against production risk while not holding back potential efficiency gains.

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Based on this, different emphases on the role of subsidy should be devised: such as increasing the conditionality of subsidies.

- 1. Conditional Subsidies:** Link subsidy payments to specific performance metrics or sustainable farming practices, incentivizing farmers to adopt more efficient and environmentally friendly methods.
- 2. Subsidy Diversification:** Explore alternative subsidy mechanisms, such as insurance schemes, price stabilization funds, or investment support, to address various aspects of risk and efficiency more holistically.
- 3. Efficiency-based Farmer Education and Extension:** Invest in farmer training and advisory services to help them optimize their operations across different levels of efficiency and leverage subsidies more effectively, reducing their reliance on subsidies in the long run.

Enhancing farmers' participation in cooperatives and the use of digital technologies for agricultural activities can be also considered as ways of improving farm performance.

Detailed research briefs are available separately for the arable and livestock farming sectors, providing comprehensive insights into methodological approaches and results.

Research brief one

**Technical efficiency and production risk in Scottish Agriculture:
Impacts on the livestock sector**

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Summary

As part of the ambition for reform of agricultural support in Scotland, farmers are expected to enhance their farm's productivity and environmental impact. Farmers may be required to adopt management measures which imply changes to farm operations in addition to compliance with basic management standards. Adoption of these measures are affected by how farmers view risk, and by the perceived effect of changing inputs on the level of production risk. Understanding what is driving production risk and technical efficiency is essential to identify farm-specific measures required to improve resilience and productivity in the farming system. In particular, whether a subsidy affects technical efficiency, production risk or both deserves special attention.

Technical efficiency indicates the rate at which physical inputs are converted into physical outputs. Best practice farms operate at the highest levels of efficiency compared to their peers. Measuring technical efficiency entails defining a frontier, which represents the maximum potential output a given farm could produce with a given set of inputs. In other words, the frontier is a benchmark against which the actual level of production will be compared. Production risk is defined as the risk arising from, e.g. weather, pests and disease, which causes variations in expected yield. We use the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data, for the period 2003–2022 to explore the efficiency of various livestock farm types, with and without accounting for production risk. Incorporating production risk allows us to accurately estimate the sources of variations in production from best practice.

We find that accounting for production risk improves the assessment of technical efficiency of all farm types, except for LFA (Less Favoured Area) dairy farms. While technical efficiency has been highly volatile over the past two decades, livestock farms are operating below their full potential implying the need for farm-specific interventions to increase farm performance. Farm subsidy is found to be negatively related to technical efficiency across all farm types; however, it does reduce production risk, serving as a risk management tool.

- Agricultural input use decisions affect output and production risk differently: it increases output and reduces production risk.
- Determinants of production risk and technical efficiency vary by farm type with consistent negative effects from farm subsidies, past CAP reform and market price shocks.
- The share of subsidies from total farm income and agricultural output price changes reduces efficiency but improves production risk for the post-2015 period.

The integration of production risk using our framework improves the overall understanding of defining best practice performance within the Scottish farm sector.

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1. Introduction

Sustainable agricultural transformation in Scotland requires improving farm performance with respect to productivity and the environment. How farmers perceive risk will affect the voluntary uptake of measures and overall investment decisions which would influence the outcomes of the new payment scheme. A previous study found that the majority of farmers in Scotland were risk averse, while around a quarter of studied farmers were evaluated as risk takers (Barnes et al., 2021).

The effectiveness of different agricultural policy measures relies on farmers' responses to risky situations. The main reason is that farmers' agricultural profit maximization behaviour is determined by their risk preference which affects input use decisions. To manage yield losses due to risks, a risk-averse farmer may use more risk-reducing (or less risk-increasing) inputs relative to a risk-neutral farmer who uses optimal input combinations. This means that a risk-averse farmer may combine inputs that yield suboptimal levels of income, negatively affecting efficiency and productivity. This further underscores that policies that disregard the interplay between risk-averse deviations from optimal behaviours and farm performance would be misleading.

Risk-adjusted technical efficiency measures the technical efficiency score after accounting for output variability due to production risk. Production risk is the variation of total output from what is achievable, which may stem from factors like bad weather conditions and the outbreak of livestock diseases. This approach also enables us to simultaneously model the determinants of technical efficiency and production risk. Different measures implemented by farmers and policymakers to augment production efficiency might also exacerbate production risk which compromises the efficiency gain. However, agricultural productivity improvement requires enhancing technical efficiency while reducing production risk. Thus, jointly studying the drivers of production risk and technical efficiency provides a broad understanding of the key areas of interventions to improve farm performance.

To this end, the main objective of this brief is to measure the trend of technical efficiency and production risk in Scotland's livestock sector. It also explores the technical efficiency and production risk determinants across different types of livestock farming systems. This advances previous production efficiency estimates (see Barnes et al. 2022 which did not accommodate production risk) and provides fresh evidence on the level of production risk and the effect of various factors on risk-adjusted technical efficiency and production risk among livestock farms in Scotland.

2. Method

The Farm Business Survey (FBS) collects detailed financial and production-related data for a set of farms in Scotland. The depth of the survey offers an understanding of the financial performance of farms over time. The sample ranges between 400 and 510 farms per year across the 2003–2022 timeframe. Using this panel we employ Kumbhakar's (2002) approach, which extends the Just and Pope (1978) method of accounting for production risk to accommodate technical efficiency and production risk in a single model.

Our modelling framework involves estimating a single random effect flexible production function in the stochastic frontier analysis framework which incorporates three components: average output, technical inefficiency component and the production risk component.

3. Results

3.1. Risk-adjusted Efficiency

Figure 1 presents the trend of risk-adjusted technical efficiency across the Less Favoured Area (LFA) livestock sectors. Except for dairy farming, accounting for production risk improves technical efficiency. **This implies that under these farming systems, production risk is prevalent, which was previously erroneously considered as inefficiency.** This means that improving agricultural productivity under these systems requires not only reducing inefficiencies but also addressing output instability emanating from production risk. The evidence is mixed for dairy farming. Accounting for production risk only improves the technical efficiency of dairy farming until the 2010 production season.

These results also highlight that, when accommodating for production risk, livestock farming performance in Scotland over the last 20 years has been highly volatile with about 21 per cent productivity loss due to technical inefficiency in some of the worst cases (e.g., dairy farming). These results suggest that there is still a potential to improve agricultural productivity by targeting these sectors with, for example, directed information and support to overcome enterprise-specific constraints.

Figure 1: Trend of LFA livestock farming TE with and without accounting for production risk.

3.2. Contribution to Production Risk

It has been long recognized that the inputs used in a production process have a varying effect on both average output and production risk. As one can see in Figure 2, our results also show that the contribution of inputs is not always the same for output and production risk. In this Figure, the coefficients map the magnitude of the impact and the error bars the 95 % confidence intervals. If they cross the red dashed line, coefficients are not significantly different from zero. The results reveal that the effect of inputs on production risk and output is farm-type specific. Focusing on significant results, the following notable findings emerge.

In most cases, an increase in the number of grazing livestock units has a synergetic effect. It not only increases output (except for LFA sheep) but also reduces production risk, thus providing a double benefit. In line with the literature, we also find that labour can significantly reduce production risk for LFA sheep and LFA cattle farms. This could be attributed to the knowledge and skills sharing required for effective farm management among employees. Here LFA farms are mostly characterised by family farming households.

Figure 2: The effect of inputs on livestock output and production risk of LFA livestock farming

Finally, land and capital are found to be risk-increasing inputs. The former increases production risk for dairy and LFA sheep farms while the latter poses a similar risk effect on LFA cattle, and LFA cattle & sheep farming. Both effects could be explained by the fact that large farms with a higher amount of land and capital restrict the farms' ability to quickly respond to unfavourable production conditions.

3.2. Determinants of technical inefficiency and production risk.

While measuring the trend of average technical efficiency provides overall farm performance information over time (Figure 1), what is equally important to policymaking is understanding why some farms are efficient relative to others. To shed some light on this question, we present significant determinants of technical inefficiency and production risk in panel A and panel B of Table 1, respectively. Positive signs indicate the factor has a significant effect that increases technical inefficiency and production risk. Negative signs indicate the factor has a significant effect that decreases technical inefficiency and production risk. Focusing on factors that consistently affect technical inefficiency across all farm types, the share of subsidies from total farm income, land tenure, farm size and market and policy shocks are prominent inefficiency determinants.

A higher share of subsidies from total farm income is associated with a higher level of inefficiency. The subsidy may shield a farm from market forces and therefore reduce farmers' participation in yield-increasing but risky investment opportunities. A similar study found negative effects on the UK's dairy farming efficiency (Latruffe et al., 2017).

However, as seen in the lower panel of Table 1, subsidies significantly reduce production risk across all farm types, denoting its role as a risk mitigation strategy. This implies that subsidies may help livestock farmers cope with uncertainties and create opportunities to take strategic actions that will transform their business sustainably, rather than being preoccupied with responding to unexpected production variabilities.

Compared with owner-occupied farms, mixed tenancy farms attain a higher level of technical efficiency, except for LFA cattle farms. Large farms are found to be more efficient than smaller ones, except for dairy farming. Large farms not only have an economic scale advantage but also a better capacity to invest in activities that improve managerial abilities, like technical skills development, advisory input and employee capacity building.

We use agricultural output price indices to measure market shocks, while policy shocks are proxied by the CAP policy changes introduced in 2015. Both shocks impede efficiency. Compared with the post-2015 period, efficiency was higher between 2003 and 2014. The post-2015 period is the most modern era where the greening of farm payments, which requires cross-compliance with greening criteria for more support of environmental goals, was introduced. Yet, the enhancement of cross-compliance measures in 2015 reduced production risk. Compared with the period before 2015, farmers attained more stable production post-2015. Since the CAP reform aimed at ensuring a more equitable distribution and targeting income support to farms in areas with high natural constraints, we would expect improved business stability for farmers in less favoured areas, in this period. Moreover, age increases production risk indicating that farms owned by young farmers face less variability in production.

Table 1: Determinants of technical inefficiency and production risk by farm type.

	LFA cattle and sheep	LFA cattle	LFA Sheep	Dairy
Technical inefficiency drivers (A)				
Loan	+			
Subsidy share	+	+	+	+
Education	+	-		
Family lab.		+		
Tenanted	-			+
Mixed tenant	-		-	-
Share of environ. area		-		
Medium farm	-	-	-	
Large farm	-	-	-	
Productive land	-	-		
Cooperative		-		
LFA ¹	+	+		
Retirement plan		-	+	-
Sole trader				+
Internet			+	
Market shock		+	+	+
Policy shock (2003-2014) [§]	+	+	+	+
Drivers of production risk (B)				
Subsidy share	-	-	-	-
Age	+	+		
Education				
Retirement plan			-	
Mixed tenant			+	
Market shock	-		+	
Policy shock (2003-2014) [§]	-	-		-
Number of farms	1,643	2,182	781	1,077

[§] compared to 2015-2022

¹ Since all our sample farms are designated as LFA farms, LFA is defined as severely disadvantaged farms.

4. Summary

- A risk-adjusted technical efficiency measures the level of technical efficiency after accounting for output variability due to production risk.
- Accounting for production risk in technical efficiency estimation more accurately reflects the conditions of decision-making on Scottish farms and adjusting for risk shows that most farms are performing at a higher technical efficiency than previously thought.
- A higher use of agricultural inputs does not necessarily improve farm performance. Some inputs increase output and reduce risk while others have a trade-off effect.
- We find that technical efficiency is constrained when the share of subsidies over total income is high.
- However, the share of subsidies over total agricultural income also helps to mitigate production risk, and reform of the CAP in 2015 helped to reduce production risk further.

5. References

Barnes, A.P., MacMillan, J., Thomson, S. G., Spencer, M., Hopkins, J., Sutherland, L.-A., & Mathews, K. (2021). Farmer Responses to Brexit: Attitudes towards Risk in Scottish Farming – Briefing Note.

Barnes, A. P. (2022). Scottish Farm Efficiency: trends and drivers from 1989 to 2020.

Just, R.E., and R.E. Pope. 1978. Stochastic Representation of Production Functions and Econometric Implications. *Journal of Econometrics* 7:67–6.

Kumbhakar, S. C. (2002). Specification and estimation of production risk, risk preferences and technical efficiency. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 84(1), 8–22.

Latruffe, L., Bravo-Ureta, B. E., Carpentier, A., Desjeux, Y., & Moreira, V. H. (2017). Subsidies and technical efficiency in agriculture: Evidence from European dairy farms. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 99(3), 783–799.

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